

The Adsorbabilities of the Ions.

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Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16 103) has proposed an interesting theory explaining the origin and the neutralisation of the charge on a colloidal particle. The origin of the charge is supposed to be due to the adsorption of ions by the atoms in the surface by virtue of their chemical affinity. On account of this charge, ions of the opposite sign are drawn near the surface. Among them, those which have their kinetic energy less than W , the energy required to separate the ion from the surface are considered as not "free". The number of such "bound" ions determines the diminution in the charge of the surface. On the basis of the above assumptions, an equation connecting θ_2 , the fraction of the original charge left unneutralised after electrical adsorption, with C , the concentration of the ion (getting adsorbed) in the bulk solution, has been derived for the idealised case in which "there is no chemical affinity acting between the ions of opposite sign." The equation so deduced has been tested and found to be of the right form to express the experimental results. An attempt is made in this paper to discuss the significance of the constants in the equations worked out.

It has been shown (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*) that

$$1 - \theta_2 = k_0 \left\{ C \cdot \frac{n_2 - n_1}{n_1} \cdot \theta_2 + C\theta_2^2 \right\}$$

where $k_0 = \frac{k_2}{k_1} \cdot n_2 \cdot u \cdot e^{W/kT}$

(Mukherjee's expression for k_0 contains the negative exponent, which is evidently a slip). The symbols employed have the following significance:

$1 - \theta_2$ = Fraction of the total charge on the surface neutralised.

n_1 = Valency of the ions chemically adsorbed.

n_2, C, u = Valency, concentration, and mobility respectively of the oppositely charged ions in the liquid in contact with the surface.

k = Boltzmann constant.

T = Absolute temperature.

W = The energy required to separate an ion from an oppositely charged surface.

k_4, k_1 = Constants for the significance of which see the original paper by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*).

As Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) points out, k_4 contains the " Nn_1 " term. Splitting it and collecting the universal constants together, we get,

$$1 - \theta_2 = k_5 \cdot ue^{W/kT} \cdot C\{n_2(n_2 - n_1)\theta_2 + n_1n_2\theta_2^2\}$$

where
$$k_5 = \frac{k_4}{Nn_1} = \frac{k_0}{ue^{W/kT} \cdot n_1n_2}$$

This constant k_5 depends only on the spatial distribution of charge on the surface and on the kinetic factors other than the mobility, determining the collision frequency.

When W is much less than kT , we can put,

$$\frac{1}{C} = k_5 \cdot \frac{\{n_2(n_2 - n_1)\theta_2 + n_1n_2\theta_2^2\}}{1 - \theta_2}$$

The right hand side expression is the reciprocal of the concentration at which a fraction $1 - \theta_2$ of the total charge is neutralised and hence can be used as a measure of the adsorbability of the ion.

We shall now proceed to work out the theoretical lyotropic series. Let A_m, A_b, A_t and A_q be the adsorbabilities of monovalent, divalent, trivalent, and quadrivalent ions respectively. Let u_m, u_b, u_t and u_q be the corresponding mobilities.

If θ_2 is very nearly equal to 1, we get, $A < un_2^2$

$$\therefore A_m : A_b : A_t : A_q :: u_m : 4u_b : 9u_t : 16u_q$$

If θ_2 is very nearly zero, $A < u(n_2^2 - n_1n_2)$

$$\therefore A_m : A_b : A_t : A_q :: 0 u_m : 2u_b : 6u_t : 12u_q$$

If $\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, $A < u(2n_2^2 - n_1n_2)$

$$\therefore A_m : A_b : A_t : A_q :: u_m : 6u_b : 15u_t : 28u_q$$

Table I gives the theoretical adsorbabilities of various ions as worked out on the above basis. Thus we arrive at the lyotropic series :

For $\theta_2 = 1,$	Th > Al > H > Ba > Sr > Ca > Mg > Cs > Rb > K > Ag > Na > Li.
$\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2},$	Th > Al > Ba > H > Sr > Ca > Mg > Cs > Rb > K > Ag > Na > Li.
$\theta_2 = 0,$	Th > Al > Ba > Sr > Ca > Mg > > H > Cs > Rb > K > Ag > Na > Li.

We shall now proceed to work out the empirical lyotropic series from the data cited by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*). As the data are limited to mono- and divalent ions we shall consider only those cases. From the general formula for adsorbability,

$$\frac{A_m}{A_b} = \frac{\theta_2}{2 + 2\theta_2} \cdot \frac{u_m}{u_b}.$$

Also we know,

$$k_s = \frac{k_0}{ue^{W/kT} \cdot n_1 n_2} \quad \therefore \quad u = \frac{k_0}{k_s} \cdot \frac{1}{e^{W/kT} \cdot n_1 n_2}.$$

If W is much less than kT , $\frac{u_m}{u_b} = \frac{2k_{0m}}{k_{0b}}$ [k_{0m} and k_{0b} are the values of k_0 for the monovalent and the divalent ions respectively]

$$\therefore \quad \frac{A_m}{A_b} = \frac{2 k_{0m}}{k_{0b}} \cdot \frac{\theta_2}{2 + 2\theta_2} \quad \therefore \quad A_m : A_b :: k_{0m} : k_{0b} \cdot \frac{2 + 2\theta_2}{\theta_2}.$$

If $\theta_2 = 0,$ $A_m : A_b :: k_{0m} : \infty k_{0b}.$

If $\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2},$ $A_m : A_b :: k_{0m} : 3 k_{0b}.$

If $\theta_2 = 1,$ $A_m : A_b :: k_{0m} : 2 k_{0b}.$

Table II gives the experimental values of the adsorbabilities calculated by the above equations. Thus the empirical lyotropic series works out to be

for $\theta_2=1$, H, Hg > Ba > K > Na

$\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, H, Ag > Ba > K > Na

$\theta_2=0$, Ba >> H, Ag > K > Na.

Thus we find that in the case of $\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2}$ the theoretical series gives Ba > H and the empirical series gives the order H > Ba. So, it would be of interest to compare the theoretical and the empirical values of the relative adsorbabilities of H and Ba over the whole range of the values of θ_2 .

$$\text{Now} \quad A_H / A_{Ba} = \frac{u_H}{2u_{Ba}} \cdot \frac{\theta_2}{1 + \theta_2} \quad \text{and}$$

(Theoretical).

$$A_H / A_{Ba} = \frac{k_{0H}}{k_{0Ba}} \cdot \frac{\theta_2}{1 + \theta_2}$$

(Experimental).

Table III gives the empirical and the theoretical values of A_H / A_{Ba} as calculated from the above formula. The theory and the experiment agree only at $\theta_2=0$. As θ_2 increases gradually to unity, the deviation also progressively increases. The maximum disparity is got when $\theta_2=1$ (i.e., in the region of dilute solutions where maximum agreement is to be expected). Throughout the H ion is adsorbed to a greater extent than what is predicted by the theory. It is seen in particular that between the limits $\theta_2=0.38$ and $\theta_2=0.54$, the theoretical curve indicates Ba > H, whereas the experimental curve shows the reverse. No doubt the theoretical curve has been derived on the assumption $W \ll kT$. Even if this simplification is not made it only makes the agreement between theory and experiment worse.

These results should not be interpreted as invalidating the general theory forwarded by Mukherjee. On the other hand, they hint at other factors which may be at play as has already been envisaged by the author of the theory. First, the interaction of the H ions with the primarily adsorbed anions is mainly of a chemical nature. The potential energy A , determining the adsorbability has to be considered in this case as consisting of the sum of W , the electrical potential energy which has been formulated for the idealised case and B , in which the potential energy arising out of all other types of interactions (such as deformation) is included. Secondly, the electrical adsorption of a divalent ion is in some respects different

from that of the univalent ion. This becomes clear when one considers the mutual repulsion between the two univalent kations when they are simultaneously electrically adsorbed by a divalent anion which is absent when a divalent kation is adsorbed; again considering the electrical adsorption by a primarily adsorbed univalent anion, it is seen that the divalent kation brings about a reversal of charge, an effect absent in the case of univalent kations. Lastly, the primarily adsorbed ions cannot definitely be known. Divalent (presumably the silicate ions) and univalent ions may both be present in this particular case. These factors account for the disparity between the theory and the experimental data, and, the existence of a general parallelism between theory and observation even when H ions are taken into consideration possibly indicates that the potential energy A (i.e., $W + B$) is the main factor in determining the adsorbability of the ions.

TABLE I*.

Ion.	Mobility.	Adsorbability for		
		$\theta_2 = 1.$	$\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2}.$	$\theta_2 = 0.$
H	314.0	314.0	314.0	0
Cs	68.0	68.0	68.0	0
Rb	67.5	67.5	67.5	0
K	64.6	64.6	64.6	0
Ag	54.0	54.0	54.0	0
Na	43.4	43.4	43.4	0
Li	33.3	33.3	33.3	0
Ba	55.4	222.0	332.0	111.0
Sr	51.9	208.0	311.0	104.0
Ca	51.9	208.0	311.0	104.0
Mg	45.9	184.0	275.0	92.0
Al	40.0	360.0	600.0	240.0
Th	23.5	376.0	658.0	282.0

TABLE II*.

Ion.	$k_0 \times 100.$	Adsorbability for		
		$\theta_2 = 1.$	$\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2}.$	$\theta_2 = 0.$
Na	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76
K	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87
H	5.9	5.9	5.9	5.9
Ag	5.9	5.9	5.9	5.9
Ba	1.63	3.26	4.9	∞

TABLE III.

	0.00	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.8	1.0
A_H / A_{Ba} (Theoretical)	0.00	0.26	0.66	0.95	1.27	1.42
A_H / A_{Ba} (Experimental)	0.00	0.33	0.84	1.21	1.61	1.81

SUMMARY.

Certain data on ionic adsorption have been considered in view of Mukherjee's theory; the adsorbability of the H ion as compared with that of the Ba ion is shown to be higher than what the formulation for the idealised case of electrical adsorption would predict which hints at importance of factors such as deformation in the consideration of the adsorbability of the H ion.

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* Tables I and II contain only the relative adsorbabilities at particular values of θ_2 . The absolute values cannot be determined as k_4 is unknown.